

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

DATA MINING TECHNOLOGY AND ITS APPLICATION TO THE SALES OF COMPUTER PRODUCTS

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ABSTRACT

In continuously developing computer products market, data mining technology has become one of the best in analyzing and optimizing sales strategies. This research aimed to obtain detailed information from complex sales datasets, and analyze them, predict the trends and help the further sales of the computer products. In the improving the sales of the computer products, this study shows the power of data mining technology by showing K-Means Clustering algorithm and how it effects the sales of computer products.

This research helps to transform raw sales data into meaningful datasets which contains useful data for examining customer behavior. Market dynamics also play an important role when trying to increase the sales, so this research helps us to examine the market dynamics on the way. Predictive models will be developed so that they help us to do all the mentioned thing and achieve our goal.

The importance of data mining is getting bigger and bigger so implementing it to the field where we want to achieve high results, which is the sales of computer products, will seemingly help us in the way. Using different methods of data mining technology, such us clustering using different algorithms helps us in different aspects, such us categorizing the customers and spending ad budget in an efficient way.

Keywords: Data Mining, Sales Analytics, Computer Products, Customer Segmentation.

1. INTRODUCTION

In today's businesses people tend to use different new technologies in order to increase the revenue, and the sales of computer products is one of those businesses. To increase the total revenue, we can use different fields of technological improvements, and data mining is one of them. We can use data mining to get the data of sales as a first step. This is because we need the raw sales data to work with. The data obtaining process is crucial, so data mining is a must in this stage. This work is aims to divide the customers into different groups, depending on different characteristics. These can be how the income of the customers, how much they spend to buy computer products, etc. We can divide them into different categories like discount seekers, frequent buyers, enterprise customer, etc.

We can use different methods and algorithms to achieve our goal. Machine learning techniques are used for data analysis and pattern discovery and thus can play a key role in the development of data mining applications [1]. K-means algorithm is preferred in this

work. We first create a raw data to work with, then implement the algorithm to partition data into categories. Organizing data into sensible groupings is one of the most fundamental modes of understanding and learning [2]. Python programming languages will be used, and the result will be displayed both as table and as a chart, in order to increase the understanding of the result. The whole process is an example of clustering. Cluster analysis is the formal study of methods and algorithms for grouping, or clustering, objects according to measured or perceived intrinsic characteristics or similarity [2].

2. STATEMENT AND SOLUTION TO THE PROBLEM

First step: The raw data

First we will have a raw data representing the customers based on their age, annual income in k\$ and spending score between 1 and 100 (a higher score means the customer spends more). By using pandas library, we create a mock data. Here is mock data:

Customer ID	Age	Annual income (k\$)	Spending score (1-100)
1	25	30	85
2	45	70	40
3	35	40	75
4	20	15	90
5	40	80	20
6	60	90	10
7	55	60	50
8	30	35	80
9	22	20	95
10	50	75	30

Second step: K-means algorithm and plotting.

We will use K-means algorithm for grouping customer into segments.

Figure 1

In this plot, we have 2 purple dots, which clearly shows high spending score and low income, they can be grouped into “Frequently buyers”.

We have 5 blue dots, which shows high income but low spending score. They can be grouped into “Discount seekers”.

Then we have 3 yellow dots representing high income and high spending score, meaning that they are “Enterprise customers”.

Thirst step: Assigning cluster labels

We can add labels to the data using pandas and here is the output:

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Customer Segments:
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CustomerID	Age	Annual Income (k\$)	Spending Score (1-100)	Segment
0	1	25	85	Enterprise Clients
1	2	45	40	Discount Seekers
2	3	35	75	Enterprise Clients
3	4	20	90	Frequent Buyers
4	5	40	20	Discount Seekers
5	6	60	10	Discount Seekers
6	7	55	50	Discount Seekers
7	8	30	80	Enterprise Clients
8	9	22	95	Frequent Buyers
9	10	50	30	Discount Seekers

Here you can see that, as we can witness from the plot previously, we have 2 frequently buyers, 5 discount seekers and 3 enterprise customers.

3. CONCLUSION

After running the calculations using K-means algorithm and plotting the results we can clearly see that we divided the customers into segments. This helps the sellers to analyze the data easily, and to know its best suited customers and tend to advertise among those customers. Consequently, it will increase the number of sales which leads to an increase in the benefit. We saw the benefit of data mining and a technique called clus-

tering, especially the K-Means algorithm. We can implement different methods and algorithms also, in order to refactor the raw data differently and to increase sales and revenue at the end.

References

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